

TINNITUS: THE PHANTOM SOUND (PART IV) – DOES NEUROMODULATION REALLY HAVE A BENEFICIAL AND SCIENTIFICALLY PROVEN ROLE IN CASES OF TINNITUS?

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The topic of tinnitus is common but complex, with three previous bulletins already dealing with this multifactorial symptom. We recommend you read the previous materials and the references consulted at the end of this bulletin.

Continuing this topic, the objective of this bulletin is to discuss the role of neuromodulation treatments in cases of patients suffering from Tinnitus Disorder.

WHAT IS NEUROMODULATION?

Neuromodulation is related to the alteration of nervous activity through electrical, magnetic, acoustic, or chemical stimuli directed to specific areas of the nervous system. The goal is to adjust, regulate, or normalize neural function that has been impaired due to injury, disease, or dysfunction. Neuromodulation can be invasive (e.g., deep brain stimulation) or non-invasive.

WHAT IS THE BASIS OF NEUROMODULATION TREATMENTS?

Neuromodulation treatments are based on fundamental principles that aim to alter the activity of the nervous system to restore functions, relieve symptoms, and improve quality of life. The bases of these treatments are as follows.

1) NEUROPLASTICITY

Neuroplasticity is the brain's natural ability to change and form new neural connections throughout life, in response to environmental modifications, whether internal or external to the subject. Internal modifications can include injury or illness, and external modifications can include experiences such as learning. Neuromodulation takes advantage of this through:

- **Induction of adaptive changes:** Neuromodulation attempts to strengthen or weaken synaptic connections, alter the level of excitation of neurons, and stimulate the growth of new neural pathways through electrical, magnetic, acoustic stimuli, or chemical agents.
- **Reorganization of brain circuits:** Neural circuits may not work properly in people who have suffered some type of brain injury or chronic pain. The goal of neuromodulation is to reestablish or "recalibrate" these circuits so that they work normally again or to compensate for any problems.

This bulletin aims to address more specifically the structural and functional changes in the brain resulting from neuromodulation by electrical or magnetic stimuli. Before we do so, it is essential to understand brain electrophysiology, specific neural targets, and some important technical terms.

Neuroplasticity

2) BRAIN ELECTROPHYSIOLOGY

The nervous system acts as a transmitter of electrical and chemical signals. Electrical signals involve action potentials, while chemical signals derive from neurotransmitters. In this sense, neuromodulation has a direct effect on electrophysiological processes, such as:

- **Modulation of neuronal excitability:** Neuromodulation techniques use electric currents or magnetic fields to alter the activity of certain neurons or neural networks, making them more active (excitatory) or less active (inhibitory).
- **Interference with abnormal activity patterns:** People with epilepsy, essential tremor, or Parkinson's disease have abnormal brain activity. Neuromodulation can disrupt or correct these patterns that are not working properly.

3) SPECIFIC NEURAL TARGETS

Neuromodulation treatments are targeted to specific parts of the brain, spinal cord, or peripheral nerves that are involved in disease. To do so, they must:

- **Identify dysfunctional circuits:** Neurological research and advanced neuroimaging allow us to identify brain regions and neural networks that are compromised in various conditions (e.g., the basal ganglia in Parkinson's disease, the motor cortex in chronic pain).
- **Selective stimulation and maximization of benefits:** Neuromodulation devices and methods are designed to send signals only to these specific targets, which maximizes therapeutic effects and minimizes side effects.

4) THE ABILITY TO CHANGE AND FLIP

Many neuromodulation therapies, especially those that use implants, are designed to be reversible and adjustable. By adjusting the parameters, it is possible to minimize possible adverse effects.

- **Parameter adjustments:** You can change the frequency, intensity, pulse width, and duration of stimulation to get the best therapeutic response and meet the patient's evolving needs over time.
- **Minimizing adverse effects:** The ability to change parameters makes it possible to adjust treatment and decrease the risk of side effects, making therapy safer and more personalized to the individual.

5) DIFFERENT STIMULATION MODES

There are different modes of stimulation and, depending on the proposed approach model, each has a therapeutic objective. Some modes of stimulation are:

- **Peripheral Nerve Stimulation:** Focuses on specific nerves (e.g., vagus nerve, peripheral nerves) that, when stimulated, indirectly influence brain activity.
- **Direct Drug Administration:** Intrathecal drug administration (as by an infusion pump) is not strictly electrical, but it qualifies as a type of chemical neuromodulation as it alters neural activity in a specific area.
- **Sensory Substitution/Biofeedback:** There are systems that induce plasticity and brain reorganization which act in an indirect way to modulate the system. This is the case of systems such as the Tongue Display Unit (TDU) or even BrainPort that do not apply the stimulus directly to the brain for neuromodulation; instead they provide modulated sensory information which indirectly modulates the system.
- **Direct Stimulation:** Application of electrical current.
E.g: Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS), Spinal Cord Stimulation (SCS), Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS), or magnetic fields such as Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS)] to directly modulate neural activity.

NEUROMODULATION AND TINNITUS

For treating tinnitus, neuromodulation presents itself as a new and promising technique. The main objective is to alter brain activity through the stimulation of specific neurobiological substrates. Because tinnitus is multifactorial, it is important to seek treatments that address all aspects of this symptom.

The experience of tinnitus can be altered by the use of neuromodulation, which works by directly suppressing or reconstructing abnormal brain activity over time.

It is important to note that the mechanisms underlying tinnitus are still under study and, therefore, there are no definitive protocols for the use of electrical or magnetic neuromodulation in tinnitus.

This approach adds to the current tools for managing tinnitus, and is innovative in that it emphasizes the modification of central neurophysiological substrates, diverging from currently available treatments which focus on patient behavior in response to tinnitus. The objective of neuromodulation is to act directly on neural networks that have been altered and are related to the underlying mechanisms. In this way, it addresses a critical deficiency in currently available therapeutic options and, for this reason, it is the subject of current scientific studies.

NEURAL CORRELATES RELATED TO THE PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF TINNITUS

Tinnitus involves both damage to the auditory system and abnormal neuronal activity in the brain, with the involvement of other brain areas. The main neurobiological theories suggest that it is caused by abnormal electrical activity in neurons of the peripheral and central auditory pathways, including the cerebral cortex.

Thus, this symptom can occur in different areas of the auditory system and, as a consequence, the areas underlying and correlated to the auditory system are affected. Auditory deafferentation, which occurs when nerve connections are lost due to peripheral hearing loss, can weaken lateral inhibition in certain frequency ranges. This, in turn, causes the neurons in the central auditory system to become more synchronized and hyperexcitable.

This hyperactivity is marked by enhanced activity, with a greater number of neural firings. This neural disorganization modifies the brain's entire ability to process sound, and there is, therefore, brain reorganization. Neuromodulation techniques aim to interfere with this maladaptive compensatory neuroplasticity underlying tinnitus. Its focus of action is the neuronal membrane potentials, the synaptic connections, and the neural firing patterns, with the aim of returning the brain to its best previous state of functioning.

This understanding of maladaptive neuroplasticity is crucial, as the foundation of neuromodulation therapies is to reverse or reorganize these abnormal neural networks, rather than just suppressing symptoms.

Predictors of Tinnitus-Related Cortical Neuron Oscillations

The perception of tinnitus is intrinsically linked to changes in the rhythmic oscillatory activity of cortical neurons. Studies using neuroimaging techniques, such as magnetoencephalography (MEG) and electroencephalography (EEG), have revealed consistent associations between tinnitus and abnormal patterns of neural activity. Notably, a decrease in power in the alpha band (8–12 Hz) and an increase in oscillatory power in the delta (1–3 Hz) and gamma (40–90 Hz) bands, are observed in patients with tinnitus (Hoares et al, 2024 and Heiland et al, 2024).

Among these changes, changes in delta-band oscillatory activity appear to be the best objective predictor of changes in tinnitus. In addition, reduced alpha activity in the auditory cortex of tinnitus patients is a recurrent finding, and increased alpha power in the stimulated auditory cortex has been associated with reduced tinnitus intensity.

The identification of these specific oscillatory signatures (delta, alpha, gamma) as biomarkers of tinnitus and its response to treatment is of great importance. This not only validates the existence of a neurophysiological basis for tinnitus, but also offers a quantifiable target for the optimization and personalization of neuromodulation therapies. If successful neuromodulation treatments reverse these specific patterns, then these patterns can serve as objective and measurable markers of treatment effectiveness, complementing patients' subjective reports.

The possibility of an accurate and objective analysis of tinnitus is intriguing and has the potential to provide a new direction in the treatment of tinnitus through the use of this biomarker.

By objectively monitoring these neurophysiological changes (e.g., via EEG/MEG), researchers and clinicians can validate the mechanisms of action of treatments, optimizing stimulation parameters (such as frequency, intensity, and placement of electrodes) to achieve the desired neurophysiological change (e.g., normalizing alpha power or reducing delta activity), and customize treatments according to the oscillatory profile and their specific responses to stimulation.

Therefore, treatments that make use of neuromodulation must be individualized and personalized for each patient. A single, global approach does not seem to benefit all patients. Considering that the symptom is multifactorial, it is necessary to emphasize that, so far, the treatment of tinnitus does not offer a single path for all and generally requires multiple approaches, with the involvement of professionals from different specialties.

Currently, there are several methodologies that are recommended in cases of tinnitus, and all the data presented below are based on published and peer-reviewed scientific studies.

NEUROMODULATION TECHNIQUES FOR THE TREATMENT OF TINNITUS

1) Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS)

Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) is a non-invasive technique based on electromagnetic induction. It generates transient magnetic fields via high-intensity pulsed current coils, inducing through the scalp and skull depolarization of cortical neurons. This modulates the excitability of neurons and neurotransmitters related to tinnitus and increases the plasticity of auditory neurons (May et. al., 2007).

In the context of tinnitus, low-frequency rTMS seems to be the most indicated, since it has been associated with inhibitory effects on neuroplasticity and reduction of neuronal hyperactivity implicated in tinnitus perception.

A relevant aspect of this methodology is the fact that it is non-invasive, painless, and safe for patients with tinnitus disorders. **However, it is important to note that although rTMS is a safe treatment for tinnitus in the short term, there is currently a lack of data proving its long-term safety (Mend et al, 2011).**

In order to understand a little more about the effects of this technique in cases of tinnitus, a systematic review and meta-analysis carried out with 16 randomized controlled clinical trials (He et al., 2025) demonstrated that rTMS can have a real impact on the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) and the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and these positive effects were observed immediately after treatment and after 30 days of intervention. These data corroborate those found in a systematic review by Yin et al. (2021), where THI scores were positively affected although Tinnitus Questionnaire (TQ) scores were not. On the contrary, a meta-analysis by Dong et al. (2020) concluded that low-frequency rTMS showed no significant benefit compared to a placebo in patients with chronic tinnitus.

Thus, there are still controversies about this aspect of neuromodulation for patients with tinnitus, so it is important that more research be conducted. According to He et al. (2025), future research should encourage randomized, multicenter, large-scale clinical trials with standardized protocols. In addition, exploring combination therapies such as rTMS with cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), rTMS combined with prefrontal stimulation, and a high-frequency protocol with auditory stimulation, would all be of great value.

2) Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS)

Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) is a non-invasive, painless brain neuromodulation technique that applies a low-intensity galvanic current (typically 1–2 mA) directly to the scalp to modulate the activity of specific brain areas.

tDCS does not directly induce neural activity, but rather modulates cortical excitability and synaptic efficiency. It affects functional connectivity, plasticity, and synchronization within various brain networks. The simplicity of operation and the affordable cost of tDCS contribute to its wide application in several areas.

According to Fortes and Sanfins (2025), due to its actions on the nervous system, tDCS has been indicated in a variety of clinical conditions such as the treatment of cognitive disorders, vestibular disorders, mood disorders, tinnitus disorders, and chronic pain, but it is important to note that in some countries such as the United States, this instrument does not yet have the approval of the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for use in medical procedures.

tDCS is able to modulate the functional connectivity of the brain network, altering the patterns of interaction and information transfer between different regions of the brain. Finally, stimulation can increase the levels and release of excitatory neurotransmitters, such as glutamate and dopamine, which are essential for synaptic maintenance and plasticity. Bifrontal application of tDCS or vagus nerve stimulation has been associated with relief of tinnitus perception, accompanied by a reduction in theta and gamma band activity in the auditory cortex.

Studies have shown that tDCS is able to effectively reduce comorbid depression in patients with tinnitus (Heiland et al., 2024). However, rTMS treatment with tDCS in the long term is questionable. The discrepancy between a clear understanding of the physiological impact of tDCS on brain activity and its inconsistent clinical efficacy points to a critical gap. The challenge lies not in the existence of a neurophysiological effect, but in its precise targeting, consistent induction, and sustained maintenance for tinnitus. This also suggests that the high heterogeneity observed in tDCS trials is a direct consequence of this lack of standardization, making meta-analyses challenging and the conclusions tentative.

3) Vagus Nerve Stimulation (VNS) and Transcutaneous Vagus Nerve Stimulation (tVNS)

Vagus Nerve Stimulation (VNS) is a neuromodulation technique that can be performed invasively or non-invasively. Invasive VNS consists of the surgical insertion of a device and an electrode designed to stimulate the cervical vagus nerve. This procedure has FDA approval for the treatment of epilepsy and depression.

In contrast, Transcutaneous Vagus Nerve Stimulation (tVNS), also known as Transcutaneous Auricular Vagus Nerve Stimulation (at-VNS), is a non-invasive approach. It stimulates the auricular branch of the vagus nerve (ABVN) located in the outer ear. tVNS is considered safer and more cost-effective than VNS, as it does not require general anesthesia and a surgical implantation procedure. Multiple neuroimaging studies have confirmed that tVNS activates the same brain networks and pathways as direct VNS, making it a viable alternative.

The neurophysiological mechanisms of VNS and tVNS in the treatment of tinnitus are closely linked to the promotion of neuroplasticity and the modulation of neurotransmitter release. VNS induces the release of neuromodulators in the brain, including acetylcholine, norepinephrine, serotonin, and brain-derived neurotrophic factor. These substances play crucial roles in promoting plastic changes in the brain (Hoare et al., 2024; Yakunina and Cheol Nam, 2021).

As for studies with tinnitus patients, it was observed that VNS and tVNS seem to perform well in the prevention and reversal of cases; in addition some studies have demonstrated a decrease in the severity of symptoms. However, according to Yakunina and Cheol Nam (2021), existing studies have important flaws, such as the absence of a control group, small sample size, lack of randomization, among others. Similarly, there is no reliable evidence to date showing that tVNS alone, without paired sound stimuli, is effective for the treatment of tinnitus.

FINAL THOUGHTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The study of neuromodulation in tinnitus patients is still under development, and there are many gaps to be filled. Tinnitus is a complex and debilitating condition whose neurophysiological underpinning is still a matter of investigation, meaning that the search for an effective neuromodulatory intervention is challenging.

Based on analysis of subjective measures for outcomes, Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) has shown potential in reducing tinnitus, especially over the short term, when directed to the auditory cortex. However, there is still a need to prove long-term outcomes. The possible identification of neurophysiological biomarkers, such as increased alpha power in the auditory cortex, presents a promising strategy for personalizing and optimizing rTMS interventions.

At the present time, Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS), suffers from a lack of standardized protocols, despite its neurophysiological mechanisms being relatively well understood. Studies are needed that analyze the long-term results of robust and consistent clinical outcomes.

Vagus Nerve Stimulation (VNS) and its non-invasive form, tVNS, represent an innovative approach, but the results in humans are contradictory, and they require better scientific studies.

Thus, neuromodulation offers a therapeutic approach to tinnitus, seeking first to correct neural dysfunctions rather than just managing symptoms. However, we need cutting-edge research that focuses on standardization of protocols, identification of objective biomarkers to guide and personalize treatment, and randomized controlled trials with larger samples and long-term follow-ups.

Detailed understanding of neurophysiological mechanisms and optimization of application strategies are essential steps to transform the potential of neuromodulation into effective and long-lasting clinical solutions for tinnitus patients.

QUIZ: NEUROMODULATION AND TINNITUS

1. Which of the following most accurately describes the concept of neuroplasticity in the context of neuromodulation?

- a) The brain's ability to remain unchanged throughout life, resisting any external stimulus.
- b) The ability of the nervous system to generate random electrical impulses without a specific purpose.
- c) The way the brain forms new neural connections and changes its structure in response to experiences, injuries or diseases, being exploited by neuromodulation to induce adaptive changes.
- d) The process of neuronal degeneration that occurs naturally with aging.
- e) The ability of certain areas of the brain to function independently of others, without any interconnection.

2. In the context of the pathophysiology of tinnitus, how does auditory deafferentation (loss of nerve connections due to peripheral hearing loss) impact the neuronal activity of the central auditory system?

- a) Increases lateral inhibition in specific frequency ranges, resulting in less synchronization and neuronal hypoexcitability.
- b) It causes a significant decrease in neuronal activity, leading to complete inactivity of auditory neurons.
- c) It strengthens synaptic connections, normalizing the brain's ability to process sound.
- d) It weakens lateral inhibition in certain frequency ranges, leading to synchronization and hyperexcitability of neurons in the central auditory system.
- e) It has no impact on the neuronal activity of the central auditory system, it only affects the perception of sound.

3. Which of the following neuronal oscillation bands has been identified as the best objective predictor of changes in tinnitus, according to studies using techniques such as MEG and EEG?

- a) Beta band (13–30 Hz)
- b) Theta band (4–7 Hz)
- c) Delta band (1–3 Hz)
- d) Alpha band (8–12 Hz)
- e) Gamma Band (40–90 Hz)

4. Low-frequency Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) could be indicated for the treatment of tinnitus due to which of its effects?

- a) Its ability to induce neuronal excitation and increase brain hyperactivity.
- b) Its action of directly inducing the growth of new complex neural pathways, without modulation of existing excitability.
- c) Its inhibitory effects on neuroplasticity and reduction of neuronal hyperactivity implicated in the perception of tinnitus.
- d) Its extremely high cost, which limits its application to a few research centers.
- e) Its need for surgical implantation, making it an invasive technique.

5. What is one of the main gaps and challenges in the use of Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) for the treatment of tinnitus, as discussed in the text?

- a) Its high current intensity, which causes significant pain and severe side effects.
- b) The lack of studies proving any neurophysiological effect of tDCS on the brain.
- c) The absence of standardized protocols, long-term studies, and robust and consistent clinical results, hindering effective analysis and application.
- d) The need for general anesthesia for its application, making it a high-risk procedure.
- e) The fact that tDCS directly induces neural activity, which is counterproductive in the treatment of tinnitus.

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Respostas Corretas do Quiz

5. correct answer: d
 4. correct answer: c
 3. correct answer: c
 2. correct answer: d
 1. correct answer: c

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- Specialist in ENT, pediatric ENT, audiology and phoniatics, and public health. Participated in the 3rd Stakeholders Consultation meeting during which the World Hearing Forum of WHO was announced;
- Member of the Roster of Experts on Digital Health of WHO, Vice-President and Institutional Representative of ISfTeH;
- President-elect of International Advisory Board of AAO-HNS, member of Congress and Meeting Department of EAONO, Regional Representative of Europe of ISA, Vice-President of HearRing Group, Auditor of EFAS, member of the Facial Nerve Stimulation Steering Committee;
- Board Secretary of the Polish Society of Otorhinolaryngologists, Phoniatrists and Audiologists. Member of Hearing Committee (2018–19);
- Goodwill Ambassador representing Poland at the AAO-HNSF 2021 Annual Meeting & OTO Experience, and since 2021 a member of Implantable Hearing Devices Committee and Otology & Neurotology Education Committee of AAO-HNS;
- Consultant Committee of International Experts of CPAM-VBMS (by special invitation), honorary member of ORL Danube Society, and honorary member of Société Française d'Oto-Rhino-Laryngologie;
- Member of the Council of National Science Center;
- Expert and member of numerous national organizations.